

Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate: Disentangled Text-Driven Image Manipulation Empowered by Pre-Trained Vision-Language Model

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Figure 1. Comparisons on disentangled image manipulation between the StyleCLIP [31] baseline and our Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate (PPE). Ours manages to manipulate only the command-attribute (as indicated under each column) while remaining unchanged to the others.

Abstract

To achieve disentangled image manipulation, previous works depend heavily on manual annotation. Meanwhile, the available manipulations are limited to a pre-defined set the models were trained for. We propose a novel framework, i.e., *Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate (PPE)*, for disentangled text-driven image manipulation that requires little manual annotation while being applicable to a wide variety of manipulations. Our method approaches the targets by deeply exploiting the power of the large-scale pre-trained vision-language model CLIP [32]. Concretely, we firstly **Predict** the possibly entangled attributes for a given text command. Then, based on the predicted attributes, we introduce an entanglement loss to **Prevent** entanglements during training. Finally, we propose a new evaluation metric to **Evaluate** the disentangled image manipulation. We verify the effectiveness of our method on the challenging face editing task. Extensive experiments show that the proposed PPE framework achieves much better quantitative and qualitative results than the up-to-date StyleCLIP [31] baseline. Code is

available at <https://github.com/zipengxuc/PPE>.

1. Introduction

Disentangled image manipulation [1, 8, 10, 12, 21, 23, 37, 38, 43, 44] aiming at changing the desired attributes of the image while keeping the others unchanged, has long been studied for its research significance and application value. Reaching this target is not easy, especially when attributes naturally entangle in the real world. Therefore, concrete attribute annotations are of vital importance, making disentangled image manipulation a labor-consuming task.

Several works [8, 10, 21, 23] use an encoder-decoder architecture and need manual annotations on multiple attributes of images. The models encode the original image and the manipulating attribute, then decode the manipulated image. Specifically, they use an attribute-specific loss to encourage the manipulation of a specific attribute while discouraging the others. The loss comes from pre-trained classifiers for all annotated attributes. Many recent works focus on latent space image manipulation since large-scale pre-trained GANs, e.g., StyleGANs [15, 16], can generate

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high-quality images from well-disentangled latent spaces. Despite the convenience of directly using the pre-trained GANs to generate images, all these methods need human annotations [1, 12, 37, 38, 43, 44]. Moreover, the available manipulating attributes are limited to the annotated set.

Recently, the rise of the large-scale pre-trained vision-language model CLIP [32] has brought a new insight. Since CLIP provides effective signals about the semantic similarity of image and text, various manipulations [11, 31, 36] can be performed with a text command and a CLIP-based loss, instead of exhaustive human annotations. Nevertheless, achieving disentangled image manipulation is still tricky. For instance, StyleCLIP [31] introduces three methods: latent optimization and latent mapper take no consideration of achieving disentangled results; global direction, which is based on the more disentangled \mathcal{S} latent space [45], needs human trials-and-errors to find appropriate parameters in each case to reach the expected effects. To only manipulate a desired attribute, TediGAN [46, 47] merely revise the latent vectors of layers corresponding to that attribute. Yet, they have to figure out in advance the relations between attributes and layers in StyleGAN.

In this paper, we explore achieving disentangled image manipulation with as less human labor as possible. We propose a novel framework, *i.e.*, Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate (PPE), to approach the target by leveraging the power of CLIP in depth. Firstly, we propose to **Predict** the possibly entangled attributes for given text commands. We assume that the entanglements result from the distributions of attributes in the real world. Therefore, we draw support from CLIP to find the attributes that appear most frequently in the command-related images, then regard the attributes of high co-occurrence frequency as the possibly entangled attributes. Secondly, we introduce a novel entanglement loss to **Prevent** entanglements during training. The loss punishes the changes of the possibly entangled attributes before and after the manipulation, so as to enforce the model to find a less disentangled manipulating direction. Lastly, based on the predicted entangled attributes, we introduce a new evaluation metric to simultaneously **Evaluate** the manipulation effect and the entanglement condition. The manipulation effect is measured based on the change of command-attribute while the entanglement condition is based on the change of the entangled attributes, before and after manipulation. All the changes are estimated according to the CLIP distance between the texts of attributes and the images.

To evaluate, we implement our method based on the simple and versatile latent mapper from StyleCLIP and conduct experiments on the challenging face editing task, using the large-scale human face dataset CelebA-HQ [14, 25]. Qualitative and quantitative results indicate that we achieve superior disentangled performance compared to the StyleCLIP baseline. Meanwhile, we show that our results present a

better linear consistency.

To conclude, our main contributions are as follows:

- We propose to predict entangled attributes for disentangled image manipulation.
- We propose a novel entanglement loss to prevent entangled manipulations during training.
- We propose a new evaluation metric that jointly measures the manipulation effect and the entanglement condition for disentangled image manipulation.
- By applying our method to the versatile StyleCLIP baseline, we manage to achieve disentangled image manipulation with very little manual labor. We conduct extensive experiments on the CelebA-HQ dataset and find that our qualitative and quantitative results are rather impressive.

2. Related Work

Disentangled Image Manipulation. Many works study learning a disentangled representation [3, 4, 9, 17, 21], so that disentangled image manipulation can be solved from the source. Due to the costly labor, a key challenge of such works is reducing the supervision for learning the desired disentanglement. Therefore, weakly-supervised and unsupervised methods have been explored [8, 10, 24, 28]. Despite progress, all these methods are trained for a fixed set of attributes, thus supporting limited numbers of manipulations.

Recently, growing numbers of works focus on latent space image manipulation [12, 13, 37, 41, 45, 48] because of the remarkable large scale GANs like StyleGAN [15, 16], which can generate high-resolution images with well disentangled latent space. Thereby, these works firstly invert the image into the latent space through the GAN inversion method [16, 50] or an involved encoder [2, 29, 35], then accordingly compute the latent vector that can derive the manipulation result through the pre-trained large scale GANs. For each manipulating attribute, manual annotations are required, *e.g.*, on images [1, 37] and on unsupervisedly discovered directions in the latent space [12, 38, 43, 44].

Text-Driven Image Manipulation. There are studies that explore image manipulation with text commands as a guide. Some previous works [6, 18, 19, 27] use GAN-based encoder-decoder architectures, which encode the original image and text command, disentangle the semantics of the two modalities and decode the manipulated image. Instead of training a generator individually, the recent TediGAN [46, 47] and StyleCLIP [31] use pre-trained StyleGAN to generate images from manipulated latent vectors. To reach disentangled manipulation, TediGAN pre-defines an attribute-to-layer map and only changes the attribute-corresponding layers in StyleGAN. Besides, TediGAN conducts instance-level manipulation, which means the model is only applicable to one image that the model was optimized for. The latent mapper method in StyleCLIP is more

general as the trained model can be applied to manipulate any in-domain image, but the results are usually entangled. The global direction method in StyleCLIP can realize a disentangled manipulation, but it requires manual trials-and-errors to find appropriate thresholds in the method. Our method proposes to achieve disentangled image manipulations with less manual effort by deeply leveraging the power from large scale pre-trained models. More than StyleCLIP, which merely minimizes the CLIP distances between command texts and manipulated images, we propose to predict, prevent, and evaluate entanglements via CLIP.

Large Scale Vision-Language Models. Following the success of large scale pre-trained language models, *e.g.*, BERT [5], various large scale pre-trained vision-language models [20, 26, 39, 40, 49] are proposed. The recent CLIP [32] is especially remarkable because it is trained from 400 million text-image pairs and is powerful. CLIP learns a multi-modal embedding space, which can be used to measure the semantic similarity of image and text. Using text descriptions as prompts enables CLIP the strong ability of zero-shot transfer to downstream tasks. Besides, stunning text-guided image synthesis results [7, 11, 33, 36] are enabled by CLIP through utilizing the embedding space.

3. Background

StyleCLIP [31] proposes a flexible latent mapper method for text-driven image manipulation. It is trained for a specific text command and is applicable for any image in the domain of the pre-trained StyleGAN [16]. For the text command t_{cmd} , the method learns a mapper network $M_{t_{cmd}}$ to yield a manipulation direction in the $\mathcal{W}+$ space given the latent image embedding $w \in \mathcal{W}+$. Then the manipulated image is obtained from a pre-trained StyleGAN generator G as $i' = G(w + M_{t_{cmd}}(w))$.

To train the mapper network for the purpose of achieving the text-driven manipulating effect, a CLIP loss \mathcal{L}_C is introduced to minimize the distance between the text command t_{cmd} and manipulated image i' . \mathcal{L}_C is formalized as:

$$\mathcal{L}_C = D_{CLIP}(i', t_{cmd}), \quad (1)$$

where D_{CLIP} is the cosine distance between the embeddings of its two arguments in CLIP space. In addition, the method uses L_2 loss to norm the manipulation direction and L_{ID} loss [35] to maintain the identity of person. Hence, the overall loss is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{StyleCLIP} = \mathcal{L}_C + \lambda_{L_2}\mathcal{L}_{L_2} + \lambda_{ID}\mathcal{L}_{ID}, \quad (2)$$

where λ_{L_2} and λ_{ID} are the loss coefficients. Although the method can simply and efficiently achieve text-driven image manipulation without human annotations, its loss cannot distinguish between entangled and disentangled manipulations, and the manipulated results are always entangled.

Figure 2. To predict entangled attributes in face editing, we construct a hierarchical attribute structure with the help of BERT [5].

4. Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate (PPE)

The proposed PPE framework consists of three parts: 1) we design a mechanism to **Predict** the entangled attributes for given text commands; 2) based on the predicted attributes, we introduce a novel entanglement loss to **Prevent** entanglements during training, and 3) we propose a new evaluation metric to **Evaluate** disentangled text-driven image manipulation. All methods leverage the power from the large-scale pre-trained vision-language model CLIP.

4.1. Predict

We predict the entangled attributes under the assumption that entanglements result from the frequent co-occurrence of attributes in real-world images. To this end, we aggregate the images most relevant to the text command, look for the attributes that appear most frequently in the images and predict them as the entangled attributes.

Prerequisite. A predefined attribute set that includes basic visual characteristics is the prerequisite. For manipulating human faces, we need human face attributes. To obtain useful human face attributes, we firstly draw support from the large-scale pre-trained language model BERT [5]. In concrete, we let BERT predict specific attributes under different categories with designed prompts like “a face with [MASK] eyes”. By substituting “eyes” with other keywords of face characteristics, we derive various face attributes in a category-to-attribute fashion.

After further sorting and adding binary attributes like “with earrings”, we construct a hierarchical attribute structure (see Fig. 2) that serves for the subsequent procedures in Predict. More details are given in Appendix A.

Aggregate. This step aims to aggregate the images that are

most relevant to the text command. Specifically, we propose a method based on CLIP. At first, we rank all the images in the training set *w.r.t.* their distance to the text command t_{cmd} in the CLIP space. For an image $i \in I$, its ranking score is formalized as:

$$score(i) = D_{CLIP}(i, t_{cmd}). \quad (3)$$

Images are ranked by their scores from small to large.

Besides, we use a zero-shot CLIP classifier to exclude the images that are classified as irrelevant in the ranked list. For single attribute manipulation, the classification labels can be obtained via a command-to-category and category-to-attributes pipeline. Take command “blue eyes” as an example, we firstly find its category $\langle eyes \ color \rangle$ with the help of an NLP tool (see Appendix B), then the labels $\{“blue \ eyes”, “brown \ eyes”, \dots\}$ can be easily obtained via a category-to-attribute map according to the hierarchical attribute structure. Particularly, binary attributes like “with earrings” will trigger binary labels as $\{“with \ earrings”, “without \ earrings”\}$. Afterwards, we select up to top-100 images in the left ranked list to form the command-relevant image-set I' . The generability is discussed in Appendix C.

Find. The last step is to find the attributes that appear most frequently in the command-relevant image set I' , except for attributes in the same category as commands. First, we rank the attributes by the sum of their CLIP distances to the images in I' . The ranking score is formalized as:

$$score_{cmd}(t_{attr}) = \sum_{i' \in I'} D_{CLIP}(i', t_{attr}). \quad (4)$$

Meanwhile, we consider the ranking results *w.r.t.* the full image set I . Similarly, the ranking score is:

$$score_{full}(t_{attr}) = \sum_{i \in I} D_{CLIP}(i, t_{attr}). \quad (5)$$

By sorting the scores in descending order, we get r_{cmd} and r_{full} . In addition, we need to find attributes that only appear frequently in the command-relevant images. For instance, “square face” is common for all images and thus ranks high in r_{full} , thus it may not be the entangled one even if it ranks high in r_{cmd} . To this end, we adjust the r_{cmd} with r_{full} . In concrete, the final ranking score is:

$$score_{final}(t_{attr}) = \frac{r_{cmd}(t_{attr})}{\min(r_{full}(t_{attr}), R)}, \quad (6)$$

where R is a hyper-parameter to determine if the rankings in r_{full} are high or not. Eventually, top- N attributes in the final ranked list (obtained by sorting the $score_{final}$ from small to large) are predicted as the entangled attributes $\{t_{entg^n}\}_{n=1}^N$.

Analysis. In Fig. 3, we illustrate some of the predictions and the corresponding manipulation results from the latent

Figure 3. Illustration of the predicted entangled attributes for various commands in text-driven image manipulation.

mapper of StyleCLIP. As can be seen, our method predicts the entangled attributes well, *e.g.*, “wide eyes” and “with makeup” for blue eyes, “grey eyes” and “white skin” for grey hair, “short hair” and “with makeup” for with earrings, and “grey hair” and “closed eyes” for wrinkles.

4.2. Prevent

For a disentangled manipulation, the command-corresponding attribute should change while other attributes should be maintained, especially for the possibly entangled ones. Therefore, based on the predicted entangled attributes $\{t_{entg^n}\}_{n=1}^N$, we introduce a novel entanglement loss that punishes the changes of entangled attributes after the manipulation. The changes are measured by the CLIP distances between images and texts of entangled attributes, thus the proposed entanglement loss is formulated as:

$$\mathcal{L}_E = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n (D_{CLIP}(i, t_{entg^n}) - D_{CLIP}(i', t_{entg^n}))^2, \quad (7)$$

where $i = G(w)$ is the original image and i' is the manipulated image as introduced in Sec. 3.

Together with the losses described in Eq. (2), our overall loss is defined as below:

$$\mathcal{L}_{PPE} = \mathcal{L}_C + \lambda_{L2} \mathcal{L}_{L2} + \lambda_{ID} \mathcal{L}_{ID} + \lambda_E \mathcal{L}_E, \quad (8)$$

where λ_E is the coefficient for the entanglement loss.

Figure 4. Illustration of (a) the effect of the entanglement loss and (b) the expected result provided by the entanglement loss.

We give an illustration in Fig. 4, where we assume there is a hyperplane in the latent space that separates having the attribute or not*, n_{gt} is the unit normal vector of the hyperplane corresponding to the command attribute, n_S is the vector found by StyleCLIP method and n_P is from PPE. As shown, the proposed entanglement loss is to constrain the model to find less entangled manipulating directions.

4.3. Evaluate

For disentangled text-driven image manipulation, we propose a new evaluation metric, *i.e.*, an indicator that evaluates the manipulation and the entanglement effects simultaneously, based on the predicted entangled attributes.

Firstly, for each text command, we quantify the manipulation effect as:

$$\Delta d_c = D_{CLIP}(i, t_{cmd}) - D_{CLIP}(i', t_{cmd}), \quad (9)$$

i.e., the change of command attribute in images measured by CLIP. The larger the Δd_c is, the closer the manipulated image to the text command is in CLIP space, indicating the manipulation reaches the command-required effect.

Meanwhile, for each predicted entangled attribute, we measure the entanglement effect by:

$$\Delta d_{e^n} = D_{CLIP}(i, t_{entg^n}) - D_{CLIP}(i', t_{entg^n}), \quad (10)$$

i.e., the change of entangles attribute in images estimated by CLIP. The larger the Δd_{e^n} is, the closer the manipulated image to the text of the entangled attribute is in CLIP space, indicating the manipulated image is entangled with the command-relevant attribute.

To reach disentangled manipulations, we expect Δd_c to be as large as possible while $\{|\Delta d_{e^n}|\}$ to be as small as possible. Thereby, we formalize the indicator as:

$$indicator = \frac{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |norm(\Delta d_{e^n})|}{norm(\Delta d_c)}, \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of the predicted entangled attributes and $norm(\cdot)$ is to make Δd_c and $\{\Delta d_{e^n}\}$ comparable. In concrete, they are normalized individually as:

$$norm(\Delta d_t) = \frac{\Delta d_t}{\max_{i \in I} D_{CLIP}(i, t) - \min_{i \in I} D_{CLIP}(i, t)}, \quad (12)$$

*The assumption draws from InterFaceGAN [37].

where t is in $\{t_{cmd}, t_{entg^1}, \dots, t_{entg^N}\}$ and I is image set.

As described in Eq. (11), assuming Δd_c is greater than 0 (as it should be), a high *indicator*, *e.g.*, 0.5, indicates an entangled manipulation, because when its Δd_c increases, its $\{\Delta d_{e^n}\}$ grows correspondingly and significantly. By contrast, a lower *indicator* indicates a better disentangled manipulation, since its $\{|\Delta d_{e^n}|\}$'s changes are not as significant as its Δd_c 's. Using the *indicator*, the effect of disentangled image manipulation can be quantified.

5. Experiments

5.1. Implementation Details

To verify the proposed method, we conduct experiments on the challenging face editing task. We compare our method with our strong baseline, *i.e.*, the latent mapper in StyleCLIP [31]. Following StyleCLIP, we use the CelebA-HQ dataset [14, 25], which consists of 30,000 images, 27,176 for train-set and 2,824 for test-set; StyleGAN2 [16] pre-trained on FFHQ [15] is used to generate images; e4e [42] is used to invert images into latent embeddings in the latent space of StyleGAN2. Moreover, we train all models following the original settings as the official StyleCLIP implementation [30]. In other words, for all text commands, we train the corresponding models without tuning the hyper-parameters. We use the same loss-coefficients setting, which is $\lambda_{L2} = 0.8$ and $\lambda_{ID} = 0.1$. For the proposed entanglement loss, $\lambda_E = 100$. The number of predicted entangle attributes N in the entanglement loss (Eq. (7)) is set to 10 by default. R in Eq. (6) is set to 40, empirically.

5.2. Quantitative Results

We conduct multiple experiments using different text commands, which especially include the ones that are regarded as entangled in previous works [21, 45]. In Table 1, we illustrate the quantitative results using the evaluation metric introduced in Sec. 4.3. In concrete, *indicator* is the overall metric for disentangled image manipulation. Lower *indicator* means target manipulation is achieved with fewer entanglements, and vice versa. In addition, $\Delta d'_c$ is the normalized Δd_c , and $\Delta d'_e$ is the normalized Δd_e , as in Eq. (9), Eq. (10) and Eq. (12).

According to the results, we draw the following two conclusions: 1) The latent mapper method in StyleCLIP is highly entangled, and our method predicts the entangled attributes well. As can be seen in the results of ‘‘StyleCLIP’’, the manipulated images are closer to text commands while they are also closer to the text of entangled attributes. For example, for text command ‘‘grey hair’’ (Table 1a), when $\Delta d'_c$ reaches 0.4878, $\Delta d'_e$ changes at a comparable scale as ‘‘grey eyes’’ is 0.2433 and ‘‘white skin’’ is 0.2641. More significantly, for text command ‘‘blue eyes’’ (Table 1k), when $\Delta d'_c$ reaches 0.4880, the $\Delta d'_e$ for ‘‘wide eyes’’ is 0.3635. 2)

		StyleCLIP	Ours	
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3359	0.0071	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.4878	0.3519	
$\Delta d'_e$	short eyebrows	0.1637	0.0261	
	short hair	0.1945	0.0445	
	with bangs	0.0927	0.0122	
	grey eyes	0.2433	0.0590	
	sideburns	0.1548	0.0195	
	narrow eyes	0.1393	0.0126	
	high cheekbones	0.0873	-0.0022	
	white skin	0.2641	0.0644	
	pointy face	0.1362	0.0161	
	with makeup	0.1626	0.0149	
(a) grey hair				
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3870	0.1266	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.3451	0.2384	
$\Delta d'_e$	short hair	0.1568	0.0525	
	with lipstick	0.1249	0.0318	
	smiling	0.1030	0.0155	
	round eyes	0.1418	0.0242	
	with makeup	0.1368	0.0221	
	brown hair	0.1927	0.0552	
	brown eyes	0.1316	-0.0239	
	with glasses	0.0640	0.0157	
	thin nose	0.1441	0.0219	
	with earrings	0.1399	0.0391	
	(d) with bangs			
	<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.4401	0.1521
$\Delta d'_c$		0.5371	0.263	
$\Delta d'_e$	green eyes	0.1867	0.0270	
	narrow eyes	0.3378	0.0672	
	dark eyebrows	0.1920	0.0251	
	with lipstick	0.1914	0.0574	
	long nose	0.2805	0.0494	
	high cheekbones	0.1708	0.0322	
	oval face	0.3418	-0.0489	
	with makeup	0.2076	0.0275	
	blond hair	0.1586	0.0181	
	rosy cheeks	0.2968	0.0472	
	(g) pale			
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.4002	0.1881	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.3585	0.1425	
$\Delta d'_e$	with lipstick	0.1783	0.0364	
	round eyes	0.1541	0.0275	
	with makeup	0.1909	0.0420	
	thick nose	0.1836	0.0418	
	round face	0.1222	0.0157	
	rosy cheeks	0.1404	0.0121	
	with earrings	0.1044	-0.0278	
	double chin	0.1633	0.0410	
	blond hair	0.1112	0.0243	
	with bangs	0.0865	0.0175	
	(j) arched eyebrows			
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.4220	0.2163	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.4880	0.2480	
$\Delta d'_e$	wide eyes	0.3635	0.1212	
	with makeup	0.2127	0.0677	
	bags under eyes	0.2702	0.1005	
	with lipstick	0.1587	0.0350	
	rosy cheeks	0.2317	0.0375	
	blond hair	0.1263	0.0321	
	round face	0.1993	-0.0518	
	pinched nose	0.1786	0.0374	
	white skin	0.2236	0.0432	
	long hair	0.0949	0.0109	
	(k) blue eyes			
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.4022	0.1691	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.2877	0.1442	
$\Delta d'_e$	blue eyes	0.1249	0.0235	
	long hair	0.1591	0.0453	
	brown hair	0.1349	0.0305	
	with makeup	0.1274	0.0249	
	wide eyes	0.1186	0.0246	
	with earrings	0.0940	0.0165	
	with bangs	0.0815	-0.0105	
	pinched nose	0.1027	0.0173	
	with lipstick	0.1136	0.0278	
	close mouth	0.1004	0.0185	
(l) with earrings				
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3269	0.1298	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.3679	0.1341	
$\Delta d'_e$	grey hair	0.2560	0.0336	
	receding hairline	0.0417	0.0035	
	no beard	0.0858	0.0119	
	long eyebrows	0.1132	0.0316	
	long face	0.1351	0.0372	
	male	0.1008	0.0035	
	narrow eyes	0.1096	-0.0065	
	big nose	0.0842	0.0013	
	black eyes	0.0937	0.0104	
	closed eyes	0.1829	0.0345	
	(e) with wrinkles			
	<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3800	0.1418
	$\Delta d'_c$		0.5579	0.2452
$\Delta d'_e$	open mouth	0.262	0.0376	
	oval face	0.2924	0.0442	
	round eyebrows	0.1990	0.0563	
	big nose	0.2588	0.0243	
	big mouth	0.2839	0.0485	
	with lipstick	0.1156	0.0144	
	sideburns	0.1311	-0.0122	
	rosy cheeks	0.1566	0.0444	
	closed eyes	0.2248	0.0466	
	bald	0.1972	0.0218	
(e) with wrinkles				
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3069	0.1491	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.4904	0.3149	
$\Delta d'_e$	arched eyebrows	0.1077	0.0270	
	close mouth	0.2105	0.0814	
	with makeup	0.2154	0.1035	
	green eyes	0.0467	0.0134	
	high cheekbones	0.1517	0.0526	
	oval face	0.1933	0.0482	
	pinched nose	0.1070	-0.0027	
	white skin	0.1668	0.0371	
	big eyes	0.1157	0.0424	
	rosy cheeks	0.1900	0.0611	
	(f) with glasses			
<i>indicator</i> (↓)		0.3703	0.2917	
$\Delta d'_c$		0.4575	0.0712	
$\Delta d'_e$	arched eyebrows	0.1425	0.0193	
	short hair	0.1369	0.0183	
	with makeup	0.2054	0.0370	
	high cheekbones	0.1553	0.0188	
	with lipstick	0.1531	0.0210	
	green eyes	0.1338	0.0115	
	round face	0.1965	-0.0233	
	with bangs	0.0992	0.0142	
	round eyes	0.1899	0.0203	
	with makeup	0.2035	0.0240	
(i) with lipstick				

Table 1. Quantitative comparison of disentangled text-driven image manipulation with StyleCLIP [31], using the evaluation metrics introduced in Sec. 4.3. For the *indicator*, lower is better. The text command is indicated under each sub-table. Specifically, we illustrate each individual item in the changes of predicted entangled attributes $\Delta d'_e$.

Our entanglement loss prevents the entanglements in image manipulation effectively. For each text command in the experiment, the *indicator* of “Ours” is significantly

lower than that of “StyleCLIP”, indicating that we achieve more disentangled image manipulation. Changes on previously entangled attributes are greatly diminished (as in

Figure 5. Qualitative comparison with StyleCLIP [31] using different text commands (indicated on the top). Ours achieves more disentangled manipulation results as only the desired attribute is manipulated while others are maintained well.

Figure 6. Image manipulation results from StyleCLIP [31] and ours, using gradually increasing manipulation strengths. Ours present better fore-and-aft consistency along the change of manipulation strength.

$\Delta d_e'$) while the manipulation effect is not affected much (according to Δd_e). In qualitative results, we illustrate that our method can achieve comparable manipulation effect with StyleCLIP when increases the manipulation strength.

5.3. Qualitative Results

Direct Manipulation Outputs. We firstly compare the directly outputted manipulation results from the trained models, without changing the manipulation strengths. In Fig. 5, we illustrate the comparing qualitative results on multiple

text commands. As can be seen in the manipulation results of “StyleCLIP”, it not only manipulates the required attributes, but also manipulates other attributes. Take text command “*grey hair*” as an example, the manipulated face gets grey hair, while it gets whiter skin and grey eyes simultaneously. Similarly, for the text command “*with wrinkles*”, the manipulated face gets wrinkles, grey hair, and more closed eyes in the meanwhile. Other manipulation results are obtained in similar conditions.

By contrast, “Ours” achieves more ideal manipulation

results, where almost only the desired attribute is manipulated while other attributes are well preserved. For example, for “wavy hair”, “Ours” hair becomes wavy while the hair length is close to the original one and the skin color does not become whiter; for “double chin”, “Ours” gets double chin while the eye color remains light brown, skin color is kept well, and mouth does not open much. In addition, it is worth mentioning that the qualitative results are quite consistent with the quantitative results, indicating that the proposed evaluation metrics are effective for the disentangled image manipulation task.

Strength-Adjusted Manipulation Outputs. We further compare the manipulation results with gradually increasing manipulation strength. To illustrate, we show four groups of comparing results in Fig. 6. In each group, we present the manipulation results for male and female, respectively. We observe that our method learns more disentangled manipulation directions compared to StyleCLIP. For StyleCLIP, when the manipulation strength increases, the desired attribute becomes more and more obvious, as well as the entangled attributes. As the male-case in Fig. 6a, from left to right, the eyes become increasingly blue while they also become wider, the face becomes whiter, and the hair color becomes lighter. Contrarily, our method presents better manipulation consistency. When the manipulation strength increases, the target attribute gradually turns apparent while others remain almost unchanged.

5.4. Discussions

Hyper-Parameters. In the previous sections, we illustrate the ability of our method to achieve disentangled image manipulation without human trials-and-errors. To further study the effects of hyper-parameters, we tune the coefficient of the proposed entanglement loss λ_E in Eq. (8) and the number of constraining attributes N in Eq. (7). We show comparing results on “blue eyes” and “with earrings”, which are found to be more entangled according to previous experimental results. As in Fig. 7a, when λ_E increases, the manipulation effects become less conspicuous while other attributes remain better. However, the manipulation effect can be enlarged by increasing the manipulation strength afterwards. As in Fig. 7b, when N varies, there are no obvious differences between the manipulation results. To conclude, our method is not sensitive to hyper-parameters.

Limitations. The limitations of the proposed PPE method are as follows: 1) Similar to StyleCLIP, the command out of the domain of CLIP and StyleGAN may not obtain ideal manipulation results. 2) The disentanglement extent in the manipulation results depends on the disentanglement extent in the latent space of StyleGAN. Since we study latent space image manipulation, the best our method can do is to find the most disentangled latent path in the latent space of pre-

Figure 7. Hyper-parameters study.

trained generator. If the attributes are originally entangled for the generator, PPE is unable to achieve completely disentangled manipulations.

Ethical Impact. One common issue in the image manipulation model is that it is biased toward the dataset the model was trained on. For example, BlendGAN [22] indicates that the ethical biases of a dataset may transfer to their model, e.g., the model outputs faces with lighter skin while the input faces are darker-skinned. Our work can help reduce this ethical impact, as our method aims at disentangled image manipulation that only changes the desired attribute while letting the others unchanged, e.g., our method can change the eye color while maintaining the skin color well.

6. Conclusion

We propose Predict, Prevent, and Evaluate (PPE) to achieve disentangled image manipulation with little manual effort by deeply exploiting the powerful large-scale pre-trained vision-language model CLIP. CLIP is leveraged to 1) **Predict** the entangled attributes given textual manipulation command, 2) **Prevent** the model from finding entangled manipulating latent directions through a novel entanglement loss, and 3) establish a new evaluation metric that can simultaneously **Evaluate** the effects of manipulation and entanglement. PPE is tested on the challenging face editing task and is proven effective.

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